

Engaging More Widely in Design Projects for Engineering Students. Student Reflections on Their Experience with Stakeholder Interaction and Empathic Imagination Tasks

Jan Van Maele¹, Diana Bairaktarova², Veerle Bloemen¹, Inês Direito^{3,4}

¹ KU Leuven, Faculty of Engineering Technology, Leuven, Belgium

² Virginia Tech, College of Engineering, Blacksburg, USA

³ University of Aveiro, TEMA, Aveiro, Portugal

⁴ University College London, CEE, London, UK

Email: jan.vanmaele@kuleuven.be, dibairak@vt.edu, veerle.bloemen@kuleuven.be, ines.direito@ua.pt

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Abstract

In this qualitative, exploratory study we analyze the reflections of engineering students after participating in a design-based team project course in biomedical engineering at master degree level at a European university. By gaining insights into how students experience a combination of real-world stakeholder engagement and empathic imagination tasks, the authors seek to inform novel approaches to fostering active, empathy-driven learning environments in engineering education. The design-based team project course aims at developing students' professional competences for addressing 'wicked' problems through active learning at iterative stages of the design process. Students are invited to engage with a wider circle of stakeholders beyond technical experts to ensure project outcomes that take the broader societal context into consideration. To this end a set of active learning tasks were developed for empathic imagination of stakeholder needs and viewpoints to complement the actual interaction with stakeholder group representatives. Data on student perspectives were collected through written end-of-project reflections of all the enrolled students (N=18). This paper analyzes the ways in which the learning tasks for stakeholder interaction and empathic imagination have impacted the student experience. Inductive coding of the data revealed eight themes, revealing students' general unfamiliarity with open projects centered on real-world problems; their understanding of the importance of communication skills and empathy; and their appreciation of the value of perspective taking through empathic imagination tasks and repeated direct interaction with stakeholders, who bring new insights that will ultimately lead to improved solutions. On the basis of the study, it can tentatively be concluded that by embedding real-world challenges, sustained stakeholder engagement, empathic imagination tasks, and iterative opportunities for feedback into the curriculum, educators can better prepare students to address the complexities of modern engineering with both technical excellence and a sensitivity that reaches out to all sentient beings.

Keywords: Design Project, Empathy, Stakeholder Engagement, Student Reflections.

1 Background and Rationale

The integration of empathy-building practices into engineering education has increasingly been recognized as critical for preparing students to tackle complex, human-centered challenges (Bairaktarova, 2022; Davis, 2018; Walther, Miller, & Sochacka, 2017). Wicked problems (Buchanan, 1992), characterized by their complexity, uncertainty, and the need for stakeholder-driven solutions, demand that future engineers engage in sustained perspective-taking and empathetic imagination (Rittel & Webber, 1973; McGowan & Settelmaier, 2022). Design thinking frameworks, especially those involving real-world stakeholders, provide a natural opportunity to nurture empathy within team-based environments (Brown, 2009; Johansson-Sköldberg et al., 2013). With respect to nurturing empathy, a growing body of research suggests that perspective-taking activities asking students to step into the experiences of others can foster deeper understanding, collaboration, and more socially responsive solutions (Liedtka, 2015). In higher education broadly, perspective-taking exercises have been shown to promote openness, critical thinking, and ethical awareness, especially when activities are carefully scaffolded, involve authentic interaction, and offer students opportunities for sustained

reflection (Gehlbach, 2004; Gehlbach, Brinkworth & Wang, 2012). Studies across higher education contexts have shown that experiential and perspective-taking activities can significantly enhance students' empathy, problem-solving abilities, and engagement (Eyler, 2009; O'Connell & Dymont, 2016). Wicked problems can serve here as a creative sensitizing tool because they call for a multi-perspectival approach (Lönngren et al., 2016). Effective empathy-focused interventions in higher education typically demand repeated exposure to diverse perspectives, opportunities for iteration and feedback, and intentional support in developing communication and reflective skills. Empathic imagination tasks (Van Maele et al, forthcoming; Walter & Sochacka, forthcoming; Zaki & Ochsner, 2012), which encourage students to mentally simulate the experiences of diverse users affected by engineering decisions, are a promising set of perspective-taking activities to complement engagement with real-world stakeholders. Integrating these activities within an experiential learning educational practice, in which students learn through direct experience and reflection, is essential for developing competencies needed to navigate complex real-world challenges (Kolb, 1984; Eyler, 2009). Building on this foundation, the current exploratory study explores how students experience real-world stakeholder engagement and empathic imagination tasks in a design team project, and how these experiences can inform approaches to fostering active, empathy-driven learning environments in engineering education.

2 Educational Context and Research Method

The current paper is part of a larger study into the potential of active and student-centered approaches, such as PBL (problem- and project-based learning), in promoting empathy development in engineering students (see Bairaktarova et al, 2024, for information on the educational contexts of the wider study). The setting of the current study is a design-based team project course for master students in biochemical engineering with a biomedical focus at a comprehensive university in Europe. This course is taught by the first and third author of this paper. The project revolves around a real-world problem introduced by a civil society stakeholder, who acts as the commissioner of the project. In this case, the manager of a horse owners' association raised grave concerns about an equine chronic liver disease that is assumedly caused by ragwort poisoning and asked the students to come up with solutions. Students worked in teams of three or four during seven full-day sessions spread out over the semester following an iterative design cycle. The approach to developing empathy was implicit in that the instructors did not mention this concept when they introduced the tasks that require empathizing on the part of the students to bring the task to a fruitful end. Instead, the various learning activities were presented as ways for students to better understand and interact with key stakeholders of the issue at hand so as to arrive at more effective designs. After identifying, analysing, mapping and prioritizing all stakeholders involved, the students developed personas for each stakeholder group, gaining an insider ('emic') understanding of how the issue at hand can impact individual members. This phase of the course encouraged teams to consider the issue from multiple perspectives before converging on their specific problem statement. This initiated a new ideation phase in which each team thought up multiple approaches for addressing the problem by putting themselves in the stakeholders' shoes, using empathic imagination tasks such as voicing personas and figure storming, in which students brainstorm from the perspective of a stakeholder persona. After selecting their specific design objectives, students created low-fidelity prototypes of their tangible solutions. Through user feedback, stakeholder interactions and cross-team discussions, students were given the opportunity to assess their initial prototype and (re-)create a modified version. In the final session of the course, students presented their solutions to invited stakeholder representatives and engaged once more in dialogue with them.

This paper presents the results of a qualitative, exploratory study that was carried out to gain more insight into how students look back on the stakeholder activities they engaged in during the design project. The primary

data source was a final course assignment, namely a reflection report of approximately 1,000 words in response to several prompts, asking about the student's experiences of engaging with the stakeholders, the emotions they experienced during the course, what they found important about the course and what they would do if there were more time available. All reports were coded inductively by the first author following a thematic analysis protocol (Braun & Clark, 2006). The coding results presented below are limited to student statements related to stakeholder interaction, the focus of the current paper. All eighteen students who participated in the course submitted the assignment and gave their consent for analyzing and reporting their work in pseudonymized form. Instructors were not aware of which students had provided approval until after submission of the course grades. Ethical approval and data privacy clearance was sought and obtained from the regulatory university committee (G-2024-7840).

3 Results

A total of 148 segments were coded in the final written reflections, representing all students in the course (N=18) pseudonymized with the initials EA, EB, ... to ER. From these codes emerged eight themes (Table 1).

Table 3. Codes and themes.

Codes	Themes	Frequency of occurrence
First time: 'stakeholders'	'First time'	<i>9 instances</i>
First time: 'real'		
First time: 'open'		
Real problem	'Real world'	<i>18 instances</i>
Real people		
Real-world		
Required: 'communication'	'Required'	<i>22 instances</i>
Required: 'active listening'		
Required: 'affective'		
Required: 'comfort zone'		
Stakeholder activities: 'insightful'	'Empathic imagination'	<i>11 instances</i>
Stakeholder activities: 'meaningful'		
Stakeholder activities: 'affective'		
Interaction: 'prior'	'stakeholder interaction'	<i>18 instances</i>
Interaction: 'commissioner'		
Interaction: 'target users'		
Effect: 'insights'	'impact as effect'	<i>28 instances</i>
Effect: 'change'		
Effect: 'solution'		
Affect: 'meaningful'	'impact as affect'	<i>20 instances</i>
Affect: 'encouraged'		
Affect: 'worried'		
Affect: 'proud'		
More face-to-face interaction	'potential'	<i>14 instances</i>
More feedback		
Communication campaign		

Figure 1. Student representation per theme

Figure 1 shows how many students out of eighteen contributed to each theme through one or more coded segments. The eight themes will now be introduced in the following five sections:

1. Qualifications of the project, comprising the themes 'first time' and 'real world';
2. Perceived requirements for stakeholder interaction, covering the theme 'required';
3. Experiences of and opinions about stakeholder interaction, comprising the themes 'empathic imagination' and 'stakeholder interaction';
4. Perceived impact of interaction with stakeholders, comprising the themes 'impact as effect' and 'impact as affect';
5. Additional potential for stakeholder interaction given more time, covering the theme 'potential'.

3.1 A Real-World Project, for the First Time

There are two aspects that stand out in how students qualified the team project course. Two thirds of the students made favorable remarks about the fact that "the course was structured around a real-world problem" [ER-1]. They believed it was "important to engage in conversations with real people" [EN-2], "actual stakeholders" who "added an element of real-world relevance" [EB-12]. The advantages of this real-world quality, according to the students, point outward in that "the project had the potential to make a difference" [EO-8] with "real-world implications" [EC-7] as well as inward in that the course set up a conducive environment for "equipping us with essential real-world skills and preparing us for professional life" [EA-3]. One student dissented, arguing that the lack of scientific data about horse casualties as a result of ragwort consumption "indicates that it is not a very relevant problem" [EP-1].

The other qualification many students (8/18) attributed to the course was its novelty in the engineering curriculum: "It was the first time in my engineering degree that I had to find a solution to a problem that was real and involved real people" [EB-4]. Overlooking prior experiences, a student points out that "in previous projects, we focused solely on identifying problems and proposing solutions, without considering the stakeholders' perspectives" [EB-3]. "To interact with the people for who [sic] we would develop our prototypes", another student confirms, 'was something that we never had to do" [EL-2]. The open nature of the project was something the students clearly appreciated: "Unlike previous projects with more rigid guidelines, we could explore various avenues and engage with stakeholders to develop meaningful solutions" [EF-2]. This was the

case even though the novelty of the stakeholder activities “overwhelmed” one student as they “grappled with the unfamiliar task of reflecting on our work from an external perspective” [EI-7].

3.2 Perceived Requirements for Interacting With Stakeholders

When students reflected on what is required for effective stakeholder interaction, they most frequently referred to the quality of their communication [12/22 codes]. Communication needs to be clear, detailed and precise in order to raise stakeholder interest and lead to useful feedback. “It was also crucial to frame our questions in non-scientific terms to ensure clear communication and understanding”, one student reports [EG-5]. Another student recommends a communication strategy with “a clear narrative that would resonate” [ED-8]. In addition, several students mention active listening as an “essential” element: “We need to actively listen to users' feedback, questions, and concerns to understand their perspectives and needs” [EH-7]. Tending to the stakeholders also extends to the written mode by “adjusting our writing style to be more empathetic and attentive” [EK-8]. Indeed, for several students the application of communication techniques go hand in hand with affective aspects. In addition to adopt an empathetic and attentive attitude, students found it was important to “approach potential users with enthusiasm and confidence” [EH-2], “to build their trust by being respectful” [EE-6], and to “maintain an open-minded approach and to take on board any constructive feedback that was offered” [EE-2]. Stakeholder interactions, one student remarks, “require us to be more authentic” [EK-9] and “demonstrate a genuine interest” [EK-7]. To put these required attitudes into practice can demand a considerable effort. As two students noted, interacting with unfamiliar stakeholders can feel “daunting” and requires stepping out of one’s comfort zone [ER-3, EC-3].

3.3 Experiences of Stakeholder Interaction

One third of the students (6/18) referred to their experiences with the empathic imagination tasks in their final reflections. As explained above, these tasks required students to venture beyond familiar perspectives on the problem at hand. One student team developed a persona for the equine stakeholder group and impersonated the voice of a horse. This was “a funny and engaging experience” [ER-6], one team member explains: even though “giving the horse a human voice was unusual for a master class”, “thinking about its life, wants, and needs provided concrete insights into what the stakeholder, the horse, would desire” [ER-7]. The created stakeholders personas also served as complementary perspectives in the figure storming activity, something that was appreciated as “crucial because it’s easy to lose sight of our goals and the people we aim to help” [EK-2]. On the whole, students who commented on the empathic imagination tasks found them meaningful, valuable, and insightful. As one student explains: “I found that the persona actually provided a surprising amount of information. It allows you to view the problem from a perspective you wouldn’t initially consider and learn to see the problem from more than one angle” [EQ-2].

Approximately two thirds of the students (11/18) articulated experiences and opinions regarding their interaction with actual stakeholder representatives, excluding any reflections on the impact of those experiences, which will be reported in the next paragraph. Three students mention how prior familiarity with certain stakeholder groups proved useful for the project: “Having been around horses since I was young, I've developed a deep connection with these animals” [EM-2]. There was widespread appreciation for the fact that there was repeated interaction with the real-life commissioner of the project. This person introduced the project during the first session, assessed the outputs at the end, and remained available during the project term, as one student attests: “we can evaluate the effectiveness of our project by talking to our client [...] after some time and asking if he sees improvements with his initial problem” [EQ-1]. Several students reflected on why specific stakeholder interactions did not have the desired effect. They attributed this to factors such as the choice of channel (“One of the problems with interacting with the user was communication, for example in

Reddit", EO-5), the limited number of representative target users that were consulted ("we only had feedback from two or three users. So, it is very dangerous to say that the entire audience group is represented", EL-4), or differences in expectations ("I think this because of the expectations that the users have, as they expect fast answers that can be implemented now, meanwhile, the solutions we provided still focused on a research stage", EO-4).

3.4 Perceived Impact of Interacting with Stakeholders

The description and assessment of the impact of their interaction with stakeholders constitutes the largest set of coded segments in the final reflection reports. The general message that emerges is that interacting with actual stakeholders brings new insights that require changes, ultimately leading to improved solutions. One student reports they "gained valuable insights from these discussions, which helped us fine-tune our prototypes to better meet user needs" [EK-6]. Another student describes the experienced effects in the following manner.

During the process of this project, we had interactions with real stakeholders that completely changed our vision and the solution we had in mind. If these interactions had not taken place, our point of view would not have changed, and we would have proposed a solution that had already been imagined or that was not feasible. [EB-5]

No fewer than 15 out of 18 students articulated this idea in some form or other. Firstly, new insights were gathered at the earlier stages of defining the problem. Students note that thanks to interaction with a "diverse group of people from different backgrounds" they acquired a "clearer idea" of the situation [EN-3] and gained insights into its "potential consequences" [EM-6]. Additional insights were gathered during the development of the solution, for instance with respect to "user's motivations and preferences" [EH-5] and "budget considerations" [EI-5]. Students report how these new insights "often forced us to rethink and adjust our initial ideas" [EB-14] and were instrumental in putting them "back on track" [EN-6] towards developing effective and user-friendly solutions.

Stakeholder interaction did not only lead to more effective solutions, it also impacted the affective realm. At least five students remark how these interactions rendered the project more meaningful to them at a personal level. Thanks to interpersonal communication, the problem was no longer "a simple statement or research goal to tackle which felt far away from my reality, it was rather a closer problem that could almost be felt as part of my reality" [EO-1]. Another student explains the affective impact as follows: "Our users could see that we were truly invested in addressing their concerns, which in turn made us more confident and committed to our work" [EK-11]. Several students point out how "positive feedback" from the target users about proposed pathways and low-fi prototypes in the course of the project served as a validation and "encouraged me to proceed further" [EJ-3]. At the same time, the real-world nature of the project also added a level of stress for some students who experienced "being worried [...] the fear that our project might not meet the stakeholders' expectations or achieve the desired impact on the community" [ED-7]. Yet, when students experienced appreciation from the stakeholders, they note this gave rise to a keen sense of pride: "We also clearly saw how his face lit up as we were explaining our idea. This made me feel very proud as it gave me confirmation that we were successful in meeting his needs and expectations" [EF-7].

3.5 Additional Potential for Stakeholder Interaction

Approximately half the students (8/18) also reflected on what they would do additionally with respect to stakeholder interaction if there were more time for conducting this team project. A handful of students explicitly mention they would invest more time in face-to-face interactions with stakeholders. As one student notes, "they often lead to more nuanced conversations and deeper connections. However, due to a lack of time

outside the project hours, I talked with them online” [EE-1]. In one way or another all reflections refer to establishing “additional connections with stakeholders” [EA-5], be it by way of more user testing, more collaboration, or more feedback. One student explicitly states these interactions take precedence over additional literature review “to increase the depth of our research [...] because I think we found enough from literature to get a good view” [ED-3]. Furthermore, “The biggest regret in my opinion is not engaging enough with stakeholders during the prototyping phase. I think getting more feedback from our prototypes could have given us the opportunity to greatly improve the final products” [ED-4]. A couple of students mention they would make additional outreach efforts in the form of workshops or a social media campaign, for instance with the purpose of making target users “aware of the [...] benefits of the rather simple solution we propose” [EB-11]. Along with further work on the prototypes, these outreach efforts could be instrumental in creating impact: “we don’t really make a big impact during the course. Just as we could really make something the project stops. In this case we could also actually help people to solve the [...] problem” [EP-5].

4 Discussion

The findings of our study reinforce the importance of intentionally integrating empathy-building practices into engineering design education, particularly when students engage with complex, real-world problems. Students’ appreciation for working with real stakeholders, many for the first time in their college experience, highlights the power of authentic, experiential learning to create engagement that the students perceived as meaningful for their design project. This aligns with research on perspective-taking activities in higher education, which consistently show that authentic interaction and exposure to diverse experiences are key to promoting empathy, critical thinking, and ethical decision-making.

The second theme where students’ emphasize the role of clear communication for effective stakeholder engagement suggests that supporting students’ development in both technical and interpersonal competencies is critical when addressing wicked problems. Communication helps students move beyond initial assumptions and engage in genuine perspective-taking, a core requirement for empathy to have a lasting effect. Similarly, the participants’ reflections on empathic imagination tasks reveal that structured opportunities for imaginative perspective-taking can deepen students’ awareness of stakeholder needs and values, particularly when scaffolded throughout the project. Perspective-taking activities, when intentionally scaffolded, have been shown to deepen student learning and commitment to user-centered problem solving (Gehlbach, Brinkworth, & Wang, 2012; O’Connell & Dyment, 2016).

The finding that stakeholder interactions led to new insights and improved solutions highlights the dynamic, iterative nature of working on wicked problems. It also underscores the need for learning environments that are flexible and open to adaptation based on stakeholder feedback. By framing design projects as opportunities to address wicked problems, educators can foster students’ ability to navigate uncertainty and develop empathy through real-world, iterative experiences (Jonassen, 2014; McGowan & Settelaier, 2022). Students’ wish for more time to build relationships with stakeholders further suggests that fostering meaningful empathy requires sustained interaction, not one-off activities. These insights align closely with the stages of the design thinking framework — empathize, define, ideate, prototype, and test — where iterative learning, real-world engagement, and empathy-driven design are essential to developing effective solutions. The students’ reflections on adapting their solutions after stakeholder feedback illustrate the importance of iteration and flexibility, core principles in design thinking frameworks (Brown, 2009; Liedtka, 2015). These findings also align with research emphasizing that empathy in engineering education not only enhances user-centered design outcomes but also shapes students’ professional identities (Walther, Miller, & Sochacka, 2017). Our findings corroborate with the literature, further suggesting that integrating experiential learning with empathy-focused

activities offers a powerful pathway for developing students' abilities to engage with societal needs and complexities (Eyler, 2009; O'Connell & Dymont, 2016).

5 Conclusion

This qualitative, exploratory study into engineering students' experiences of stakeholder engagement in a project course shows that students appreciated the commissioned design project for its real-world implications and the opportunities to engage with stakeholders through actual interaction and empathic imagination tasks. Students highlighted that stakeholder engagement brought them new insights that required changes, ultimately leading to improved solutions and a sense of validation. Adjustments in their communication and an empathetic and authentic attitude were considered key to success. Collectively, these align with recent calls in engineering education to integrate human-centered design approaches that emphasize iterative engagement with stakeholders (Woolard & Carlson, 2020; Johansson-Sköldberg et al., 2013). The results suggest that in order to nurture active learning and empathy in engineering education, teachers must develop competencies in designing authentic, flexible, and reflective learning experiences. In the following step we will apply the same methodology to data collected in a design-based project team course data North American engineering college where empathy was an explicitly named focus of learning activities. This will shed further light on our tentative conclusion that by embedding real-world challenges, sustained stakeholder engagement, empathic imagination tasks, and iterative opportunities for feedback into the curriculum, educators can better prepare students to address the complexities of modern engineering with both technical excellence and a sensitivity that reaches out to all sentient beings.

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